

THE FIGHT AGAINST POVERTY IS ENSURING PERSONAL ECONOMIC SECURITY

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Abstract

The article examines the theoretical and legal aspects of poverty, the causes of poverty in society. The most widely used types of poverty line in the country, the level of poverty, the economic security of the person, the main direction of human security, and the theoretical approaches are researched. Scientific suggestions on reducing poverty in the Republic of Uzbekistan were also given.

Key words: State budget, social policy, education, social protection, social sphere, health care, poverty.

"President of the Republic of Uzbekistan Sh. In his Address to the Oliy Majlis, Mirziyoev stated for the first time that there is a poor population in our country, they make up approximately 12-15 percent of the population, that is, 4-5 million people. Until that time, the concept of "poor population" was used in our republic. The word "poor" was never mentioned. Our president proposed to develop a poverty reduction program together with the World Bank, the United Nations Development Program and other international organizations, and to conduct in-depth studies on the basis of international standards and create a new methodology covering the concept of "poverty", its definition criteria and assessment methods. determined the task" [4].

In the economic literature, "poverty is an indicator of the economic status of individuals or social groups who do not have the opportunity to meet the minimum needs necessary for living, maintaining the ability to work, and continuing the unity of generations, and the social group or individual meets the minimum needs necessary for life. it is a characteristic that reflects the economic conditions of the inability to get it" [7]. Poverty is a relative concept and depends on the general standard of living in each society.

Economic security of a person is one direction of human security. Based on the definition of the UN Development Program, human security means "freedom from want", "freedom from fear" and "living with a sense of self-worth" and based on them, development and respect for human rights along with security risks. the main attention is paid to the problems. Experiencing poverty and poverty is an economic threat for a person and indicates that his economic security is not ensured. One of the important components of human security is defined as freedom from poverty, freedom from fear and living with a sense of self-worth. "Danger to people is to their survival (physical exploitation, torture, persecution, death), to live (unemployment, health, danger, food shortage) and to know their value (restriction of human rights, understanding that it can be considered a threat to inequality, racial discrimination). Therefore, the fight against poverty and poverty and their reduction is one of the important directions of ensuring personal economic security.

Researcher B. According to Khamidov, the most commonly used types of poverty line are: poverty level based on nutrition; international poverty line; relative poverty line; subjective poverty line.

Researcher M. Muhammedov said that two categories of poor people can be considered, the first category of poor people is those who do not want to improve their lives, but are too lazy to try. The second category is a person who has become such a person due to certain reasons, who wants to work, but for some reason has not been able to do so," he says. "In our opinion, the poor can be divided into three groups. The first category includes the unemployed, people who have appropriate qualifications but cannot find a decent job. The second category includes people who are employed, but whose income is not enough to lift their family out of the poverty line. The third is the segment of the population that does not have the opportunity to work (such as children with disabilities, incapacity for work, children and the elderly) [8].

Decree No. 5975 of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated March 26, 2020 "On Measures to Fundamentally Update the State Policy on Economic Development and Poverty Reduction" aims to improve the living standards and quality of the population in the regions, and in particular, to reduce poverty, to increase the competitiveness of all branches and sectors of the economy. and new and stable work due to the creation of fundamental conditions for the development of entrepreneurship it is directly related to the organization of seats", it was noted. This, in turn, requires ensuring the coordination of activities of ministries and agencies related to the structural reform and development of the economy, increasing the responsibility of each official, and introducing a system based on modern and innovative principles based on the rapid identification and elimination of existing problems and obstacles.

Based on the above, the level of poverty is, in general, a relative concept, and poverty depends on the level of general well-being in a particular country. According to scientists and experts, the level of poverty is divided into two types: absolute and relative. Different criteria are used, the poverty line in rich countries is higher than in poor countries. People living in absolute poverty can only meet the minimum needs that ensure biological survival. Relative poverty means that the level in one country differs from that in another, or that the level of poverty also increases or decreases over time. There are several approaches to measuring poverty.

In our opinion, it would be appropriate to include the following among the issues that cannot be delayed in our country in order to eradicate poverty:

- development of specific organizational, economic, legal mechanisms for reducing poverty in our country, introduction of criteria for determining the level of poverty and assessment methodology, taking into account foreign experience;
- development of minimum standards and regulatory frameworks of social security and establishing wide use in practice;
- qualitative development of the labor market and its composition, analysis and improvement of the processes of labor migration, as well as the implementation of the principle of self-employment of the population while carrying out mutually compatible work on the distribution of labor resources, and starting to solve the employment problem;
- study the living conditions and social condition of its citizens in each neighborhood, develop the methodology for calculating the minimum living wage and the minimum consumption basket, and ensure their compatibility with state targeted programs.

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